

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D3.3 GOhydro mobile application

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ACRONYMS LIST

AI	Artificial Intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
MAC	Media Access Control
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WYSIWYG	What You See Is What You Get

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the operational framework and design of the GOhydro Mobile Application, responsible with the interaction that happens between the platform and the end-user. The Mobile Application will extend and complement the functionalities of the GOhydro Digital Platform, making it a complete solution for using it.

The report describes in brief the design and implementation of the GOhydro Platform's User Interface. Finally, the report clarifies the architectural placement of the UI components in the context of the Digital Platform that serves the overall GOhydro solution.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims to develop a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in any hydroponic installation. In the bigger picture, the project aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

Towards this objective, the provision of robust, accurate predictive models that will determine the state of the cultivation based on sensing data and provide actionable guidance to the users is one of the core aspirations of the project and the GOhydro product itself. In this context, WP3 aims to put in place the AI framework that will make the most of the available data and the deep insights built in the context of WP1 and constitute an effective and performant recommendation and decision support sub-system.

D3.3 deals with the design and development of the mobile application. Research, as well as company development experience in the WEB industry, have provided a well-rounded solution, based on an extensible framework with readily available secure components. The Mobile Application has been developed as a progressive web application, that is accessible and installable from any device, including (but not limited to): mobile phones, laptops, tablets, desktop devices, IoT endpoints that provide graphical user interfaces (e.g.: Raspberry PI with a connected monitor). Requirements are kept as low as possible, accessible with only a browser that has been updated to the latest version.

2 SCOPE OF THE USER INTERFACE COMPONENT

2.1 OVERALL CONCEPT AND PURPOSE

The User Interface (UI) concept and purpose must be viewed within the GOhydro project. One of the objectives of the project is to provide an easy-to-use and easy-to-understand user interface, that will provide all the available information about the system. The learning curve required for the adoption of this system and its UI should be as low as possible, with an opt-in strategy that would allow any user to access more information on the topic that is currently being viewed or opened.

The design of the platform UI was done by implementing parts of User Experience (UX) design paradigms and empirical guidelines, that were researched by the design team. The users' needs were brainstormed and elicited by discussing with enthusiasts and every aspect that surfaced from this process was considered in the design of the UI. A/B testing and multiple feedback sessions were held to have a clear and concise overall view of what the UI should look like. The following UX principles were considered when designing:

- **Meeting the users' needs**, or what the user expects to find within the application;
- **Designing a clear hierarchy of entities**, or what are the real entities that are modelled by the system;
- **Consistency**, as a key aspect of design quality, so that the experience will be uniform across the system;
- **Accessibility**, as every entity and piece of data should be in a clear place and be as easy as possible to be found;
- **Context and user behaviour**, as the users will not have their undivided attention to the application, so the design will have to take this into account.

The purpose of the UI, thus, is to provide a simple and intuitive interface to the data platform, that is abstracted and implemented as simply as possible. The UI will also provide access to the Knowledge Base, which is comprised of several knowledge articles that could be of good use to the user (depending on the specific of the user's interests).

2.2 DATA REPRESENTATION

Data Transfer happens on at least two levels, within the GOhydro Platform. Level 1 marks the transfer between the endpoints (actual installations) and the Data Ingestion System (Quantum component), while Level 2 transfers the data from the Quantum component to the GOhydro User Interface, to be processed and displayed to the end-user. The data has a specific format, based on JSON standard, that is validated at arrival by the UI component.

At each request, the UI component compiles a list of active installations, along with their sensor kit serial number and communication device serial number. The date range for each of the installations is taken from the UI's internal database which holds all the important information about all the installations. The Quantum component will return an array of updated data that will be cached locally and used whenever a user visits the platform. Statistical information is computed on the spot by the User Interface and provided to the user.

Furthermore, each training session accepts as input the parameters of the recipe applied in the current cultivation cycle, as well as the measures for determining yield quantity and quality reported in deliverable D4.1. These are measured post-facto after the yield has been collected and uploaded to the data platform with the same identifiers, to be incorporated into the training set.

3 DESIGN & EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 DESIGN OF THE UI ENTITIES

The implementation of the user interface started by establishing the typology of the person who will use the platform (Persona). For the GOhydro project, the following characteristics of the Persona that will use the platform were defined:

- is between 30 and 40 years old;
- lives in the city, in an average apartment, with enough additional space;
- works in a medium-sized company, which ensures a stable and predictable work schedule;
- has enough free time for study;
- passionate about technique;
- passionate about healthy eating habits;
- with a sincere interest in environmental protection and fuel economy;
- wants the opportunity to grow his own food;
- passionate about individual study and individual discovery.

As can be seen from the Persona, the user has the curiosity, resources and determination to be able to acquire, build and use a complete GOhydro system. Persona is also passionate about system monitoring, being interested in tracking the values displayed by sensors, time series, yields and any other values the platform displays through the interface provided.

For these reasons, the interface must meet all the requirements in a way that is simple enough to be pleasant and intuitive to use, but also detailed enough to have access to any kind of information that might be available, either as a read value by a sensor, either as a result of various statistical calculations.

The user interface features different entities, modelled after physical entities, for ease of understanding and working with the platform. They are arranged in a tree structure, as follows:

- **Facility** is a physical location where one or more grow trays can be found. Each user can have several installations;
- **Grow tray** contains one generation of a given plant (at a given time). An installation may contain several trays, and a tray will contain only one species of plant, at the same point in the life cycle;
- **The sensor kit** is an assembly for reading and transmitting data to the transmission mode. Each transmission module can support up to 8 sensor kits. They are powered by a powerbank and have local storage, in the event that the connection to the transmission module is lost;
- **The data transmission module** has a processor that makes the connection between the sensor kits and the cloud platform;

In the first instance, we can divide entities into simple physical entities and electronic components. The correspondence between these is not 1 to 1, but rather n to n . A plant can have several grow trays. A data transmission module can connect with a maximum of 8 sensor kits. However, one or more sensor kits can be connected within an installation. A sensor kit can also serve one or more trays.

Figure 1 shows how to display a customer's installations. There is the possibility of defining a new installation, by using the button marked accordingly. For each installation, you can configure (Figure 4) the parameters that will be displayed in this general list. The purpose of the parameters is to give the user a quick overview of all plants and their overall health, or growing conditions. By carefully monitoring parameters such as temperature, certain anomalies such as accelerated cooling can be detected early.

Figure 1 Display the installations screen

To obtain more information, the user can select a specific installation, using the Show Details button. Executing this operation will display the interface in Figure 2. Here we will be able to observe the different plant trays that have been defined by the user. For each of these, the temperature history for the last two weeks can be accessed. This diagram is obtained by clicking on the indicator related to the desired parameter.

Figure 2 Showing a setup with two planter trays

This window will also contain information about the progress of the plants, data about the growth recipe (environmental conditions), as well as suggestions extracted from the artificial intelligence module. The user can configure the name of the installation, give it a description (in which he can put any details he wants, such as the physical location of the installation), as well as define physical trays that are placed within the installation. Each defined tray will have access to the data from the associated sensor and estimates can be made on it.

Figure 3 Creating a new tray within an installation

Setting up a tray within the application involves setting its name. Here the user can use any name he wants so that he can track a large number of trays and make the association with the physical tray. In addition to the name, it is also necessary to select a growth recipe and a sensor kit that will be associated with the tray. Multiple trays can be associated with the same sensor kit and the platform will display the data in a contextual way, also considering the data associated with the tray in the estimations made by the machine learning platform.

Figure 4 General settings for an installation

Figure 4 shows the general settings of the currently selected installation. On the left side, you can choose the sensors whose values will be displayed on the page with the list of installations (Figure 1). Each user can choose for each individual installation which sensors he wants to be displayed, depending on the relevance he considers each type of sensor to have. The setting can be changed whenever the user wants. On the right side of the settings window, we find the name and description of the current installation, as well as the temporal resolution with which the sensor graphs are displayed.

Figure 5 The settings for a tray within an installation

Figure 5 shows the settings and operations for each rack in the current installation. The name, recipe and sensor kit are configured on the left side of the screen. On the right side we can access two actions, namely the restart of growth (which signals to the platform that a new generation of plants has been introduced) as well as the removal of the tray from the installation.

Figure 6 List of log entries for a specific installation

Logs (see Figure 6) are events within the platform that can be seen as a history. These can be of several types, such as **Notices, Alerts, Errors**. These events can be added automatically by the platform, but the user can also manually add entries to the Log.

Figure 7 Record height for a specific tray

The application allows recording the height of the plants, through the screen shown in the Figure 7. This recording is then used within the platform's machine learning algorithms to assess the current state and make predictions based on that state.

Figure 8 History of temperature values for a specific tray

The history of temperature values can be seen by opening the corresponding screen. The screen will contain the graph of the values as well as statistics about this data such as minimum, maximum and average values. These charts can also contain Log entries, so that possible correlations between variations and different events can be quickly observed.

Figure 9 Connecting a data transmission module to the online platform

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the two states (initial and after configuration) of the system with a controller and a sensor kit. The available operations depend on the context of the application, so in the initial phase the user can only associate a data transmission module with his account. Each such module contains a Raspberry PI microcontroller, which has a MAC address (reference something) associated with it. Within the graphical interface, this MAC address will be entered, thus enabling the platform to receive data from this microcontroller.

A similar operation is done with the sensor kits, which in a similar way have a MAC address that will have to be associated with the user account and with a certain data transmission module. The software components, specially developed for this application, will be downloaded and installed by the user on the cards related to the microcontroller systems.

Figure 10 Connecting a sensor kit to the online platform

After installing the software components on the card, they are ready to use. With the first start, they are self-configuring, automatically generating all the files necessary for their correct operation. After starting, the system searches for Internet connection and starts sending data to the cloud platform, data that will automatically be associated with the connected user account.

3.2 KNOWLEDGE BASE

The GOhydro project is aimed at both amateurs and professionals in the field of vertical farming. Therefore, the level of knowledge that each category of people has can vary a lot, this aspect reinforcing the need for a knowledge base accessible to all.

Within the user interface component, a user-accessible knowledge base module was developed, taking into account the following requirements:

- The user interface must be simple and intuitive, taking into account UX aspects;
- The information will be compiled in articles, which may be accompanied by images (image gallery) and video;

- Articles will be grouped into categories, each article can belong to only one category;
- Each article will be able to be linked to another article, which deals with a similar topic;
- Users will be able to mark favourite articles (**Love** button), thus increasing the importance of these articles.
- Users will be able to distribute articles in at least three ways (both social networks and instant messaging services);
- The knowledge base must be searchable so that information is easy to find.

Figure 11 The user interface for the knowledge base within the GOhydro project

Analysing these requirements, the necessary entities were modelled and the actual interface was sketched with the help of the UX team. As can be seen in Figure 11, the knowledge base interface contains the following elements:

- In the upper-right part we find the **filter field**, which can be used to search for items in the knowledge base. The search is done both in the title of the article and in its body, using the GET parameter of the request to the server, in order to be able to save the search, return to it, or share it with other people;
- Between the search field and the list of categories is the section of the page where the current location was displayed within the knowledge base (**Breadcrumb**). This area will allow the user to know their exact location at all times. The user can choose to return to the parent category, to see and open other articles with the same theme;
- The category list initially displays all existing categories in the knowledge base. If the user chooses a category, all subcategories will be loaded in this area, thus allowing a quick and intuitive navigation through the category tree structure;
- Following the list of categories is the list of items available in the currently selected category and all its subcategories. Available articles have several possible operations on them, such as saving it to a list of favourite articles (the **Like** operation), opening the article (by clicking on the image or title), or sharing it on a network of social media, using the buttons related to each individual article.

Within the article found in the knowledge base, we have access to various functionalities, as can be seen in Figure 12. At the top, the article header, the current location within the knowledge base

(**Breadcrumb**) can be seen, similar to the category display. This location will be useful for visitors to correctly interpret the location and navigate within the knowledge base.

The actual article consists of a title, content, as well as a photo gallery. Content can be entered and edited via a WYSIWYG (**What You See Is What You Get**) editor. Thus, images, videos from various sites that offer this functionality (YouTube, Vimeo, etc.), tables, lists and formatted text can be inserted. All these functionalities will help editors to design articles that will explain in a complex and complete way certain concepts, ideas, tutorials.

On the right side of the page, we find the action bar (**sidebar**), where you can see the basic image of the article, the sharing buttons on instant messengers and social networks, as well as a list of related articles (linked between them). Thus, terms associated with the current article can be defined as well as series of articles with a common theme, which must be read in a predetermined order (such as the case of tutorials).

The image gallery is at the bottom of the article page. Here you will be able to see all the images that have been uploaded for the opened article, with the possibility of opening any of them. Once an image is open, navigation between them is done using the arrows on the keyboard or by clicking on the image, on the related controls.

Figure 12 The design for a knowledge base article

4 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

This report serves as a companion to the GOhydro UI implementation, providing more insight into the UI's design considerations that were relevant to the graphical design and high-level programmatic design of its components.

It is meant as a low-tech summary of the involved technologies and architectural choices, with the programmatic documentation of the components being a distinct outcome of the relevant GOhydro activities, to be available online and attached to the actual source code of the components.

As the described solution evolves and matures, the report will reflect these developments, updating the relevant descriptions and providing links to the relevant repositories where source code and documentation reside.

The next step in the pertaining activities is the link between the GOhydro UI and the GOhydro Data Platform, which provides full-duplex communication and data exchange between components and local installations. The first deployment of the operational environment will follow, along with all the required available options, like user management, data access, GDPR compliancy and subsequent requirements.